

Metadata descriptor for the datasets and codes provided in the study

Column Name	Description	Unit	Data Type
Location ID	Unique identifier assigned to each selected location globally	None	Integer
Country	Name of the country in which the inland water is located	None	String
Latitude (Decimal Degrees)	Latitude of the inland water polygon centroid in decimal degrees	Decimal Degrees	Float
Longitude (Decimal Degrees)	Longitude of the inland water polygon centroid in decimal degrees	Decimal Degrees	Float
Size Class	Categorical classification of the inland water polygon based on area (e.g., Small Inland Water; SIW (<10 <i>ha</i>), Medium Inland Water; MIW (10-1000 <i>ha</i>), and Large Inland Water; LIW (>1000 <i>ha</i>))	None	String
Split	Indicates whether the inland water polygon was used in the training or testing set for model development	None	String
System Type Area (km ²)	Surface area of the inland water polygon	Square Kilometers (km ²)	Float
Circularity Ratio	It is the ratio of the inland water polygon area to the circle area with the same perimeter	Dimensionless	Float
Compactness	It is the ratio of the inland water polygon's perimeter to its area	Dimensionless	Float
Lemniscate Ratio	It is the ratio of the area of the lemniscate having the same length as the inland water polygon to the inland water actual area	Dimensionless	Float
Elongation Ratio	It is the ratio of the diameter of a circle with the same area as the inland water polygon to the polygon's maximum length	Dimensionless	Float
Expert-annotated System Type	Expert-annotated and cross-validated system type labels, i.e., lentic ("1") or lotic ("0")	None	Boolean